

Beckmann Transformation of 2,5,6-Trimethoxyindan-1-one Oxime

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The title compound on Beckmann transformation is cleaved to 2-cyano-4,5-dimethoxyphenylacetaldehyde.

Fragmentation of β -keto ether oximes under Beckmann conditions into nitriles, carbonyl compounds and alcohols has been reported to be a general reaction¹. Although such fragmentation reaction with a variety of α -oximino ethers has been studied^{1,2}, indanone ether oximes have received no attention. The availability of 2-alkoxyindan-1-ones³ prompted us to study the Beckmann transformation with the oximes of this class of

compounds and as an example we chose 2, 5, 6-trimethoxyindan-1-one oxime(I) for our investigation. When subjected to Beckmann transformation with polyphosphoric acid, the oxime (I) afforded 2-cyano-4,5-dimethoxyphenylacetaldehyde (II) in 29% yield; with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in pyridine or aqueous sodium hydroxide the yield of the nitrile was only 15%.

Based on mechanistic consideration for the so-called 'abnormal' Beckmann rearrangements, Ferris⁴ concludes that nitriles are formed from oximes having *anti*-configuration, whereas *syn*-oximes are transformed into isonitriles. The course of fragmentation in our case may, therefore, be represented as follows:

1. R. K. Hill, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 29.

2. C. A. Grob and P. W. Schiess, *Angew. Chem. Internat. Ed.*, 1967, **6**, (I), 1.

3. P. K. Banerjee, D. Mukhopadhyay and D. N. Chaudhury, *This Journal*, 1965, **42**, 115.

4. A. F. Ferris, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 12.

The second-order reaction pathway for the *anti*-configuration involves the departure of the hydroxyl with its bonded pair of electrons with simultaneous shift of an electron pair *only* forming the carbon-nitrogen triple bond and hence the nitrile. The intermediate carbonium ion then combines with the hydroxyl ion and completes the reaction by expelling methanol to form the aldehyde (II). The low yield of the nitrile (II) does not exclude the possibility that the oxime (I) could be a mixture of both *syn* and *anti* forms. On the other hand, it is possible that the reaction condition not being optimum the yield is poor, although the oxime has solely the *anti*-configuration.

For our work 2, 5, 6-trimethoxyindan-1-one (III) was prepared by adopting the reported procedure³ for the preparation of 2-alkoxyindan-1-ones. 2-Benzoyloxy- (IV) and 2-ethoxy-5, 6-dimethoxyindan-1-one (V) were also similarly prepared. Incidentally, these preparations substantiate our earlier observation³ that acid-catalysed decomposition of 2-diazoindan-1 ones in alcoholic solutions does not take the normal course. Oximation of (III) furnished the oximino ether (I) which when subjected to Beckmann transformation with polyphosphoric acid at 65° for 12 minutes afforded a product, m.p. 102°. The conditions stipulated were found to be optimum since at 100-120°, the temperature recommended for such fragmentation reaction or longer reaction period at lower temperatures gave only intractable products. With *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in pyridine or in aqueous sodium hydroxide the same product, m.p. 102°, was obtained but in much lower yield.

The structure of the transformation product melting at 102° was established as 2-cyano-4, 5-dimethoxyphenylacetaldehyde (II). It readily reduced Fehling's solution and gave a crystalline 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. Oxidation with silver oxide followed by hydrolysis yielded 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid, m.p. 215-216°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen⁵. Vac-sublimation of the acid furnished 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic anhydride, m.p. and mixed m.p., 175-176° with an authentic sample⁶ of the anhydride.

Hill¹ observed that nitriles are obtained in the Beckmann transformation of β -keto ether oximes with *p*-toluene-sulphonyl chloride, whereas polyphosphoric acid at 100-120° gave amides, formed by the hydrolysis of the initially formed nitriles. But in our case, the nitrile (II) was the sole product both with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride and polyphosphoric acid. It is apparent that hydrolysis of the nitrile with polyphosphoric acid does not take place at the lower temperature 65°, employed.

EXPERIMENTAL*

2, 5, 6-Trimethoxyindan-1-one (III). It was prepared by adopting the reported procedure⁷ for the preparation of 2-alkoxyindan-1-ones. 2-Diazo-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one⁷ (6 g.) was dissolved in MeOH (120 ml.) on warming, the solution cooled to room temperature and treated with 1N. H₂SO₄ (4 ml.) when N₂ briskly evolved. After the reaction subsided, it was refluxed on water bath for 0.5 hr., water (60 ml.) added and most of the methanol distilled off. The residual solution was extracted with ethyl acetate (100 ml. × 3), the

*All m.ps are uncorrected. Microanalyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford.

5. W. H. Perkin (J.) and R. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 1081.

6. N. K. Bose and D. N. Chaudhury, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, 20, 49.

7. N. K. Bose and D. N. Chaudhury, *This Journal*, 1965, 43, 211.

extract washed successively with water, aq. bicarbonate, water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent gave yellow needles, the benzene solution of which was chromatographed through a column of Brockmann alumina using benzene as the eluent. The residue left after distilling off the benzene was crystallised from ethyl acetate to afford pure (III) as colorless needles (5.3 g.), m.p. 102° . It can also be purified by vac-sublimation. (Found: C, 64.5; H, 6.6. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 64.8; H, 6.3%).

2-Ethoxy-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one (V). It was prepared *as above* from 2-diazo-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one⁷ (1 g.) in ethanol (50 ml.) and 1N. H_2SO_4 (0.7 ml.). Evaporation of the ethyl acetate extract gave a solid which was crystallised from ethyl acetate-petrol ether (b.p. $60-80^\circ$) to furnish pure (V) as colorless needles (0.5 g.), m.p. $95-6^\circ$. (Found: C, 66.4; H, 7.0. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 66.1; H, 6.7%).

2-Benzoyloxy-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one (IV). 2-Diazo-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one⁷ (1.8 g.) dissolved in benzyl alcohol (50 ml.) was treated with 1N. H_2SO_4 (1.5 ml.) and the solution heated on water bath for 20 min. Water (50 ml.) added and benzyl alcohol was removed by steam distillation. The aqueous solution was extracted with ethyl acetate, the extract washed with water, aq. NaHCO_3 , water and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solid left after evaporating the solvent was crystallised from ligroin to yield (IV) as colorless rods (0.6 g.), m.p. $128-9^\circ$. (Found: C, 72.1; H, 6.3. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 72.4; H, 6.04%).

2,5,6-Trimethoxyindan-1-one oxime (I). (a) A mixture of (III; 2.2 g.), barium carbonate (1.98 g.) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.4 g.) in ethanol (35 ml.) was refluxed for 7 hr. The insoluble material was filtered off, the alcoholic solution concentrated and poured into water. The precipitate obtained was crystallised from methanol to give the pure *oxime* (I) as colorless rods (2.3 g.) m.p. $156-7^\circ$. (Found: C, 61.0; H, 6.6. $\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{NO}_4$ requires C, 60.7; H, 6.3%).

(b) A solution of (III; 1.1 g.) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.35 g.) in pyridine (10 ml.) was set aside for 48 hr. and then poured into water acidified with 2N. HCl. On standing for a week, crystals gradually separated which were collected and crystallised from isopropanol or benzene-ligroin to afford (I) as colorless rods (0.75 g.), m.p. $156-7^\circ$, undepressed with the specimen obtained as under (a).

Beckmann transformation of 2,5,6-Trimethoxyindan-1-one oxime (I). (a) *With PPA*: The oxime (I; 1 g.) was stirred with PPA [from P_2O_5 (7.5 g.) and orthophosphoric acid (4.5 ml.)] at 65° for 12 min. and then poured into crushed ice. Next day, the solution was extracted with ether, the extract washed with aq. NaHCO_3 , water and dried (Na_2SO_4). The residue left after evaporating the ether, was taken up in benzene and chromatographed through a column of Brockmann alumina using the same solvent as the eluent. Benzene was distilled off and the solid residue, on three crystallisations from ligroin yielded the pure *nitrile* (II) as colorless prismatic needles (0.25 g.), m.p. 102° . (Found: C, 64.2; H, 5.1. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_7\text{NO}_3$ requires C, 64.3; H, 5.3%). Its *2:4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone*, prepared by the method of Shine⁸, formed maroon needles (from diglyme), m.p. $244-5^\circ$. (Found: C, 53.2; H, 4.2; N, 18.3. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_5\text{N}_5\text{O}_6$ requires C, 52.9; H, 3.89; N, 18.18%).

(b) *With tosylchloride-pyridine*: A solution of the oxime (I; 1.2 g.) and TsCl (1.05 g.) in pyridine (10 ml.) was allowed to stand at room temperature for 48 hr. and then poured into ice-water acidified with HCl. The aqueous solution was repeatedly extracted with

ethyl acetate, the extract washed with 2N. HCl, water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent left a gum, which on several triturations with petrol ether (b.p. 40-60°) solidified. It was dissolved in the minimum quantity of hot benzene and left for several days when crystalline material separated out. It was collected and recrystallised from benzene to afford the *unchanged oxime* (I) as colorless rods (0.04 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 156-7°.

The benzene mother liquor was evaporated, the residue extracted with boiling petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) (20 ml. $\times$ 3), and the solvent distilled off from the extract. The solid residue was crystallised from ligroin to yield the *nitrile* (II) as colorless prismatic needles (0.13 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 102°.

(c) *With tosylchloride-NaOH*: A solution of the oxime (I; 1.2 g.) in 10% NaOH solution (14 ml.) was treated portionwise with TsCl (1.1 g.) during 25 min. A little sticky material that remained undissolved was filtered off, the solution acidified with dil. HCl (1:1) and filtered from traces of suspended impurities. It was extracted with ethyl acetate, the extract washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent gave a sticky solid which was extracted with boiling petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) (15 ml. $\times$ 3). Evaporation of the solvent gave a crystalline solid which on recrystallisation from ligroin yielded the *nitrile* (II) as colorless prismatic needles (0.11 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 102°.

Conversion of 2-Cyano-4, 5-dimethoxyphenylacetaldehyde(II) *into 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid/anhydride*. The nitrile (II; 100 mg.) was added to mixture of AgNO_3 (170 mg.) in water (1 ml.) and 10% NaOH (10 ml.), heated on water bath for 4 hr. and finally refluxed on free flame for 1 hr. Next day, it was filtered from the mixture of Ag and AgOH, a pallet of NaOH added to the filtrate and the solution refluxed for 8 hr. It was then ether extracted and the extract discarded; the aqueous alkaline solution was acidified and concentrated on water bath. It was cooled, filtered from traces of impurities and thoroughly extracted with ether. The ether extract, after drying (Na_2SO_4), was evaporated and the solid residue crystallised from boiling water (charcoal) furnished 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid, m.p. 215-6° (decomp.), undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen⁵.

The homophthalic acid obtained from the *nitrile* (II) was vac-sublimed (bath temp. 165-168°/0.4 mm.) and the sublimate was crystallised from benzene to afford 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic anhydride, m.p. 174.5°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen.⁶